

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Ahmad****FIRST NAME: Mubshar****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is basic format that is to be followed to cite books?

- Authors Name. Date. *Book Title*. Place of Publication: Publisher.¹**
- Authors Name, Book title, Date, Place of publication.
- Authors Name, Book title, Date, Publisher.
- Authors Name, Book Title, Date, Page Number.

2. How to insert footnotes after punctuation in Word document?

- Using footnote requires reference at the end of paper .
- Can only cite either in sentence between “” or as a separate paragraph.
- Do reference, insert footnote, enter footnote #, enter reference.
- Do Reference, Insert Footnote, enter standard reference format.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 3rd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 15.

² *Ibid.*, 16.

3. **What does primary resource refers to in three kind of research resources?**
- Books, articles, papers, reports.
 - Textbooks, encyclopedia, Wikipedia, dictionaries, articles.
 - Texts, letters, objects, maps, survey, government database.**³
 - Search engines like Google, librarian, academic writings, literatures.
4. **What does paraphrase means?**
- To write point of a passage, section, or whole article or book.
 - Must replace most of words of the original with own.**⁴
 - Record exact quotations for purpose of evidence to back up reasons.
 - Paraphrase is never as good as direct quotation.
5. **How to guard inadvertent plagiarism?**
- Always identify words from a source you cannot mistake them.**⁵
 - Paraphrase a source so closely that a reader can match.
 - Do not need to acknowledge anything that you did not create.
 - Record quotations and paraphrases without quotation marks.
6. **During research, how can one manage moments of normal anxiety?**

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 36.

⁴ Ibid., 50.

⁵ Ibid., 51.

- You can minimize anxiety by organize and summarize what you have gathered by writing as you go.⁶**
- Taking the notes but not organizing.
- Not referring friend, classmates, teachers, sympathetic critical audience.
- Not returning to central questions: What question I am asking? What problems I am posing?

7. **What are 4 reasons for citing your resources?**

- Never give credit for work that is not your own.
- To give credit, to reassure accuracy of facts, to show readers the research tradition, help readers extend your research.⁷**
- Rephrase and take credit, assure accuracy of facts, shows readers research tradition, help readers extend your research.
- Not allowing others to extend the research work.

8. **What cyclical tasks include in qualitative dissertation process?**

- Reading, planning, writing.
- Qualitative dissertation appears complex and one cannot master.
- Qualitative dissertation is linear, but rather iterative and recursive.
- Reading, planning, writing, collecting data, analyzing data, interpreting and synthesizing findings, developing conclusions.⁸**

⁶ Ibid., 55.

⁷ Ibid., 140.

⁸ Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. Completing your qualitative dissertation.(Chicago: Sage Publications, 2008), 27.

9. **How to identify and retrieve literature?**

- Look for essential components in literature.
- For research articles, extract technical elements and establish matrix.
- Search library, familiarize with online database, try out general descriptors, obtain theoretical and empirical literature.⁹**
- Ensure your arguments flow logically and coherently.

10. **What is the largest challenge on the environment?**

- The emissions of greenhouse gases and their effects.¹⁰**
- Oil price fluctuations and US recession.
- Integration of solar PV systems and wind energy.
- Ethical and economic challenge of unequal burdens of ecological impacts.

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Linda Dale, Bloomberg and Volpe, Marie. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*. Chicago: SAGE Publications, 2008.

⁹ Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie, Volpe. *Completing your qualitative dissertation*. (Chicago: Sage Publications, 2008), 77.

¹⁰ Alejandro, Nunez-Jimenez. "Energy policy for the transition: Designing policies for harnessing technological change." (PhD Diss., Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Zurich, 2020), 21.

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